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Optimal production and maintenance scheduling for a multiproduct batch plant considering degradation

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ABSTRACT

Performance decay due to asset degradation is an important constraint in industrial production and therefore needs to be actively considered. This paper focuses on short-term scheduling for multiproduct batch processes with sequence-dependent degradation and is motivated by a case study in which the sequence of multiple-grade batch runs impacts evolution of fouling. A continuous-time scheduling formulation is proposed to incorporate realistic features of the case study processes. The precedence scheduling concept for the sequential process is employed to model sequences of multiproduct orders and maintenance and is implemented using the general disjunctive programming method. The scheduling formulation is applied to the case study and further analyzed through comprehensive computational tests, which illustrates the efficacy of the proposed formulation.

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1. Introduction

The topic of joint production and maintenance scheduling has been popular in literature for decades. Industrial process units usually exhibit various types of degradation such as aging, fouling, wear, deformation, etc. (Martin et al., 1983; Bott, 1995; Zmitrowicz, 2006), which leads to performance decay during production and eventually becomes the termination criteria of production campaigns. In such a case, maintenance is required to reverse the degradation effects and needs to be considered while scheduling the production. Integration of production and maintenance in scheduling improves production performance when compared to the case where two problems are solved in a separate manner, in which preventive maintenance is performed to have a minimal effect on production (Dedopoulos and Shah, 1995). Therefore, degradation, being one of the main factors that affects production and maintenance, should be actively considered in scheduling. As a result, degradation models are built and employed to simulate the evolution of degradation, which are further integrated into op-

timization frameworks for scheduling. Various types of degradation have already been modeled in literature (Zhang et al., 1999; Teruel et al., 2005; Yeap et al., 2004; Wu et al., 2019a), and a review for degradation modeling approaches can be found in Gorjian et al. (2010). Accordingly, scheduling of production and maintenance are formulated using various types of mathematical programming formulations. Therefore, one challenge still remaining is to find appropriate scheduling formulations and degradation model structures that can be effectively combined to incorporate realistic processes features.

Recent examples from literature of production and maintenance scheduling are summarized as follows: Castro et al. (2014) presented a continuous-time model for maintenance scheduling in a gas engine power plant, which used multiple time grids and precedence-based sequencing variables for maintenance team and gas engine scheduling; the model was derived using generalized disjunctive programming (GDP) and compared both big-M and convex hull reformulations to find an appropriate set of constraints. Xenos et al. (2016) focused on optimal operation and maintenance scheduling in networks of compressors for chemical plants, where two types of washing procedures are considered with the aim of reducing extra power consumption due to fouling in the compressors; they proposed a discrete-time mathemat-

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